

careables.org

D2.3

Open

Healthcare Map

v2

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The final version of the Open Healthcare Map is an interactive online map that can be updated easily and continuously by the community to be kept up to date.

Community members can register and update the map. The Open Healthcare Map can be found here: <https://www.welder.app/careables>

We added a recent section focussing on careables in the context of COVID-19. While the main content is online, we have created a visual index of the **171 projects**¹ that can currently be found on our platform under the tag *careables*.

Additionally, we want to refer to an introduction to the user interface and the steps needed to add content to the Open Healthcare Map on Welder. This can be found as Appendix 1 in the deliverable D3.3 as well as [online](#)².

¹ <https://www.welder.app/projects?tags=careables>

²

<https://www.careables.org/resource/documenting-careables-projects-on-welder-app-how-to-do-it/>

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1. Introduction

In this document, we provide a visual index of the **171 projects** on <https://www.welder.app/careables>. The Open Healthcare Map v2 is primarily accessible online and is equipped to be continuously updated and to be expanded by the community. The repository is growing further and can best be looked at online. This document provides an alternative way to access the projects by listing them in alphabetical order.

2. Categories and Tags

Figure 1: Seven of nine categories and the COVID-19 Banner

The Open Healthcare Map v2 is an online repository and is structured into the following **9 categories**³:

- LEARNING/COMMUNICATION (19)
- MOBILITY (22)
- OUTDOOR INSTALLATIONS (7)
- INDOOR INSTALLATIONS (5)
- SELF CARE (19)
- THERAPY (18)
- DAILY LIVING (43)
- CAREWARE (13)
- FUN/LEISURE (43)

³ The numbers in the brackets indicate how many projects are listed in each category.

Additionally, there is one category to channel the solutions related to the COVID-19 pandemic (compare Figure 1):

- COVID-19 (37)

Furthermore, there is a wide list of tags to choose from, which are shared with the general welder.app platform.

Distribution of projects and categories

Each project can be found in several different categories, or also be not attached to any of the categories. This depends on what the users submitting the projects choose, from the options available.

As indicated in the list of categories, **DAILY LIVING** and **FUN/LEISURE** have the most entries with **43 project entries** each, followed by **MOBILITY** with 22, **SELF CARE** and **LEARNING/COMMUNICATION** with 19, and **THERAPY** with 18 entries.

INDOOR INSTALLATIONS has the least entries with 5, **OUTDOOR INSTALLATIONS** has 7, and **CAREWARE** 13. This could indicate either, that users of the Open Healthcare Map v2 have not created many solutions fitting into these categories. or alternatively, that these categories are hard to grasp for users.

Because of the ongoing pandemic situation, we added the **10th category** on **COVID-19**. In this category, we currently have **37 projects**.

41 projects have not been put in any of the currently 10 categories suggested, but either have only the *careables tag* or other tags, which are often more related to the technical realization. The reason might be, that users find other tags more suitable, or think in different categories. Through the user interface, we could enforce choosing at least one of the main categories, but we did not implement it in this way.

3. Visual Index

As the main element of the Open Healthcare Map v2 is the online repository, we provide this visual index of all of the projects. As projects can show up in several categories, or in none, this list is sorted in alphabetical order, with the name in the left column, the main thumbnail picture in the middle, and the link to the project in the right column.

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
3D printed custom orthotics		Link
3D printed orthotic swimming fin		Link
3D printed Wheelchair Ramp for one step		Link

Table 1: Visual index 3D-3D

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Adaptable Drinking Aid		Link
Adaptive Jacket		Link
Adaptive seat fixture for kayaking		Link
Adjustable Mouse for Hilga	<p>Open Health HACKademy</p>	Link
Adjustable Shopping Trolley-THE CITY aid		Link

Table 2: Visual index Ad-Ad

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>Afstandsbediening voor slechtienden</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>ALL CNC MADE FACE SHIELD-REUSABLE-OPEN SOURCE-QUICK PROD</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Assist Twist-Jar Opener and Closer</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>BauhausUniVisor-One-Minute Lasercut Covid-19 Faceshield</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Bike Adaptation</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 3: Visual index Af-Bi

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2

<p>Braille Keyboard Covers Keys</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>buzzme</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Camera Aid</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>camping lift for wheelchair users</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>CapraSTICK</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 4: Visual index Br-Ca

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Chill Pill		Link
Color detector		Link
Conspicio		Link
Corona door handler		Link
Covid-19 Basic Protection Kit		Link

Table 5: Visual index Cc-Co

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>COVID-19 Decontamination Toolkit</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Crutches Pads</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Crutch Tip Rubber Foot Adapter</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Cupholder</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Custom Assistive Spoon</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 6: Visual index Co-Cu

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>Customizable Wrist Brace</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>da-vi-do</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Disabled Hoist Lift</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>DIY COVID-19 protective mask-Science Camp</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>DIY-Pelvic and Thoracic guider for walking</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 7: Visual index Cu-Di

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>Door Opener and Push Button tool</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Door Openers Recap</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Double reusable frame</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Drawer Opening Assistive Device</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Drifter Car-A Students Project</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 8: Visual index Do-Dr

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>Dynamic Minerva for Head Support</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Easy COVID 19</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Easy Zipper for Assistive Technology Challenge</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Electric Wheelchair kit</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Enzyme Dispenser Mechanism</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 9: Visual index Dy-En

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
EVS eye vibration sensor		Link
EyeTracktive		Link
Eyewriter		Link
FABI-Flexible Assistive Button Interface		Link
Face Shield Model Tropical Bauhaus		Link

Table 10: Visual index EV-Fa

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2

<p>FaceShields for Laser Cutter</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Faceshields Recap</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Fast Printable face shield</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>FI-CO Fingers Counting</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>FINGER EYES for BLIND READING</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 11: Visual index Fa-FI

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>Finger Step Ladder</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Fixperts</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>FLipMouse</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Foot-controlled Robotic Arm</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Fu Face Mask with lining for filter</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 12: Visual index Fi-Fu

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Go-Kart for a special child		Link
Gudret		Link
Hack a toy		Link
Hackcess Handy Holder		Link
Hand Drive		Link

Table 13: Visual index Go-Ha

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Hands-Free Door Opener		Link
Hands free suitcase puller-life hack		Link
Hat Shield Cofree		Link
Head-mouse game controller		Link
Helpers Helper		Link

Table 14: Visual index Ha-He

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Hospital Scrubs		Link
How to reuse masks and respirators in emergency cases		Link
Humanoid Robotic Hand		Link
Ice Cream Aid		Link
Innovative Assistive Tech-iASSIST		Link

Table 15: Visual index Ho-In

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2

interdental brushes holder		Link
Intubation Boxes Recap		Link
Intubation station		Link
IntuPlex-3mm		Link
IO SSISTENZA		Link

Table 16: Visual index in-IO

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Joystick adapters kit		Link
KAEPSELE		Link
Keyguard for MacBook		Link
Liftable Hanging Planters		Link
Light Doorbell		Link

Table 17: Visual index Jo-Li

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Lil		Link
LipSync		Link
Low Cost Ventilator Solution		Link
Low Vision Measuring Cap		Link
Lupo white cane tip		Link

Table 18: Visual index LI-Lu

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Made in shoes		Link
MakerMask project		Link
Medical-grade stethoscope		Link
Medisch hulpmiddel-afstap loopband		Link
Mounting Baby Seats To Wheelchairs		Link

Table 19: Visual index Ma-Mo

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2

<p>Mouse moved by the mouth</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Moving3Dmachine</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>MY FACE MASK</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>My space helmet</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Nailcutter for one hand</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 20: Visual index Mo-Na

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>Nanohack</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Nintendo switch pro controller handicap mod</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Novel Transparant Face Mask</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Odyschrift Connect Four</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>One Handed Cutting Knife</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 21: Visual index Na-On

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>One hand pot opener</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>OpenBraille</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>OPEN LIGHTS</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Open Pump</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Open Source Leg</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 22: Visual index On-Op

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Open Trailer		Link
Oskar Zither		Link
Oxygen tank roller		Link
O_Zwo		Link
Parametric 3D Mask		Link

Table 23: Visual index Op-Pa

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Parkinsons Step Stick		Link
PD gardening kit		Link
PILL DISPENSER		Link
PillStorage Fits All		Link
Pimping my Cane		Link

Table 24: Visual index Pa-Pi

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>Plastic bottle opener for hand support</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Playshade</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Posterior Harness</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Print your mask</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Protective Face Mask</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 25: Visual index PI-Pr

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>Prothese voor hand-links en rechts handig</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Prusa Protective Face Shield</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Push button tool for kids</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Push up bar</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>PVC-foot</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 26: Visual index Pr-PV

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>Quali-fire</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Reading Aid</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Reindeer Game Controller</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Removable door handle opener</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Removable Mid-Step II</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 27: Visual index Qu-Re

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Removable Mid-Step		Link
Rijido		Link
Rollavie modified walker		Link
SEDIA A DONDOLO ESISTENZA CATALANO PERILLI PORTA VAGHI		Link
Signature Guide		Link

Table 28: Visual index Re-Si

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2

<p>Slide N Shop</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Slit lamp</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Smart Toys</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>SOS-vibrating bracelet</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Squeeze-a-ring</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 29: Visual index SI-Sq

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Stadiometer		Link
Stomanoir HvA		Link
Stomanoir new		Link
Stress-Reducing Weighted Blanket		Link
SunnyGlass		Link

Table 30: Visual index St-Su

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2

<p>supporto tiflotecnico</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Svens Special Trike</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Tap adapter</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>T-CUP</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>TestCupHolder</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 31: Visual index su-Te

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>The Chill Pill--Insulin carry pill</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>The EZegg</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Thumb Prosthesis</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Toilet Paper Holder for Disabled Access Hand Rail</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Toiletrolhouder voor mensen met een arm</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 32: Visual index Th-To

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
Tools for dealing with paralysis of the arm		Link
Toothbrush Adapter		Link
TooWheels		Link
Video magnifier for people with low vision		Link
Voice2Hand		Link

Table 33: Visual index To-Vo

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2

<p>Wc seat adaptor for Chiara</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>We Will Scoot</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Wheelchair Accessible Picnic Table</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Wheelchair rain cover</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>Wheelchair Simulator</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 34: Visual index Wc-Wh

Visual Index Open Healthcare Map v2		
<p>WHO-recommended Handrub Formulations</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>WiiMote Modification for Persons With Disabilities</p>		<p>Link</p>
<p>XMonitor-Low cost vital signs monitor</p>		<p>Link</p>

Table 35: Visual index WH-XM